

Predicting Thermal Comfort in Buildings With Machine Learning and Occupant Feedback

Panagiotis Skaloumpakas
HOLISTIC IKE
Athens, Greece
pskaloumpakas@holisticsa.gr

Elissaios Sarmas
Decision Support Systems
Laboratory, School of Electrical and
Computer Engineering
National Technical University of
Athens
Athens, Greece
esarmas@epu.ntua.gr

Zoi Mylona
HOLISTIC IKE
Athens, Greece
zmylona@holisticsa.gr

Alessio Cavadenti
ASM Terni S.p.A.
Terni, Italy
alessio.cavadenti@asmterni.it

Francesca Santori
ASM Terni S.p.A.
Terni, Italy
francesca.santori@asmterni.it

Vangelis Marinakis
Decision Support Systems
Laboratory, School of Electrical and
Computer Engineering
National Technical University of
Athens
Athens, Greece
vmarinakis@epu.ntua.gr

Abstract—This scientific paper discusses the importance of thermal comfort control in buildings for providing high-quality working and living environments. The paper proposes a machine learning-based approach for assessing thermal comfort, which incorporates feedback from building occupants and installed temperature sensors. The approach aims to provide a more accurate estimation of thermal sensation and facilitate energy management for building managers through the provision of precise predictions of thermal comfort, thereby supporting effective HVAC control actions. The approach is characterized by its reliance on external and internal temperatures of the building, as well as human responses to a plain thermal comfort questionnaire, to evaluate the thermal comfort of the occupants in different spaces. The paper describes a methodological approach to enhance the accuracy of thermal comfort evaluation in an iterative fashion without causing discomfort to occupants. The effectiveness of the proposed approach was demonstrated through its validation and testing at the ASM Headquarters. Neural networks were initially utilized to forecast the hour-ahead internal temperatures of the different offices and the external temperature of the building. Afterwards, classification models were deployed to predict the thermal sensation of the occupants providing a useful input for an HVAC controller or for controlling natural ventilation in the building in order to maintain the occupants' environment comfortable.

Index Terms—thermal comfort, occupant feedback, temperature sensors machine learning, neural networks, HVAC control

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermal comfort is a key factor in creating a satisfactory working and living environment, as it directly influences the occupants' mood and productivity. The definition of thermal comfort is subjective, and it reflects an individual's satisfac-

tion with the thermal environment [1]. Maintaining indoor conditions within specific ranges is necessary to ensure thermal comfort, as prescribed by various standards for thermal comfort [2]–[4]. Building operators and HVAC designers have widely used the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) model, which builds on P.O. Fanger's thermal comfort theory [5], [6]. PMV takes into consideration both environmental (temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature, and air speed) and personal (metabolic rate, and clothing insulation) factors to determine whether the indoor conditions are sufficiently comfortable for the occupants. Sensors can now be placed in any room, enabling the simultaneous monitoring of the environmental conditions of different office spaces, such as temperature and humidity. However, individual factors can vary widely among individuals, making it challenging to measure them accurately and precisely, which can cause an unsatisfactory thermal experience for the occupants during the operation of the building. This is especially important in workplaces and office buildings, where sub-optimal indoor environmental conditions are often associated with a reduction in productivity [7], [8]. As a result, the PMV model has been reported to have many biases, including overestimating cooling requirements in hot climates, resulting in unnecessary energy waste. Incorporating direct feedback from building occupants regarding their perceived comfort levels, through the development of user-friendly applications, can help overcome some of these limitations. Gathering responses from occupants can yield more detailed and personalized insights that account for individual variations in thermal comfort perception, potentially enhancing HVAC control [9]–[12].

Additionally, as data science continues to progress, an increasing number of researchers are directing their attention towards utilizing machine learning (ML) algorithms to construct data-centric models that can forecast the thermal comfort of occupants. ML algorithms can be used to analyze data from various sensors in the building and occupant feedback, providing a promising solution for building managers seeking to ensure occupant comfort. In [13], the superiority of personalized measures for thermal comfort compared to standard non-adaptive methods was showcased and a methodology using Logistic Regression to convert user votes to a probability of comfort was deployed. In [14], two field investigations were conducted on the indoor thermal environment and human adaptation in residential buildings with district heating in Harbin during two winter seasons. The investigations included measurements of physical environmental parameters as well as subjective questionnaires and an ordinal Logistic Regression model was used to detect whether people felt “cool” or “warm” with relatively good accuracy. ASHRAE Global Thermal Comfort Database II was analysed in [15] to identify which subjective metrics should be used for the assessment of the occupants’ thermal experience and found that the thermal sensation is the most frequently used. Afterwards, Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine were used to predict thermal acceptability and preference. Decision Tree was used in [16] to predict the occupants’ thermal sensation using skin temperature measurements of seven selected body areas in conjunction with a thermal sensation and comfort survey. Historical air temperature to quantify the thermal history was proposed and used to predict thermal comfort and thermal demand from physical or physiological parameters in [17]. Specifically, five local skin temperatures (at hand, calf, head, arm and thigh) and the heart rate in conjunction With the proposed historical air temperature used as inputs in the classification tree model provided the best accuracy. Four different state-of-the-art models, including Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, Ensemble Algorithms, and K-Nearest Neighbor were used in [18] for predicting winter individual thermal comfort using environmental and biological data as input. Authors in [19] also used different ML models such as Support Vector Machine with four different Kernel functions and Ensemble Algorithms to predict an individual’s thermal preference with input data from a personal comfort system, skin temperatures, time and environmental data. Thermal comfort models based on kNN, RF and SVM were developed in [20], outperforming the PMV model. In the article, feature ranking showed that insulation, indoor temperature, and relative humidity were the most significant features for the thermal sensation prediction.

The thermal comfort assessment approach proposed in this paper serves a dual purpose. Firstly, it aims to provide a more accurate estimation of thermal sensation by incorporating feedback from building occupants and installed temperature sensors. Secondly, it aims to facilitate energy management for building managers by providing precise predictions of thermal comfort, supporting practical HVAC control actions. More specifically, the assessment approach is characterized

by its reliance on external and internal temperatures of the building, as well as human responses to a plain thermal comfort questionnaire, to evaluate the thermal comfort of the occupants in different spaces. This approach offers a robust evaluation of thermal sensation without the need to consider specific building characteristics and difficult-to-measure parameters such as occupants’ clothing and activity levels. As a result, it presents a promising avenue for scalability.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. General Overview

A right-now or point-in-time survey was deployed and occupants were asked to vote about their thermal sensation on a 7-point scale, ranging from -3 (cold) to $+3$ (hot), based on the ASHRAE-55 standard.

TABLE I
ASHRAE 55 THERMAL COMFORT VOTES (7-POINT SCALE)

Vote	Cold	Cool	Slightly Cool	Neutral Comfortable	Slightly Warm	Warm	Hot
Value	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3

Initially, it was administered to all occupants during specific hour intervals over a period of one month to collect sufficient data to train different classification models. Afterwards, in order to reduce the burden of constantly asking occupants to report their thermal comfort, an online web-interface was deployed to enable occupants to complete the questionnaire at their convenience and feed more data to the classification models.

Simultaneously, deep learning models were used to forecast the hour-ahead internal temperatures of different offices and the external temperature of the building based on the recorded historical data of the installed sensors. Afterwards, the forecasts were fed into the classification model to give an hour-ahead prediction of the average thermal sensation of the occupants depending on the office of the building. The thermal comfort prediction of the occupants can provide a useful indicator for building managers to make adjustments in the HVAC system by increasing the cooling or heating of the corresponding office in order to maintain the environment comfortable. The overview of the proposed methodology is shown in Figure 1.

B. Class Reduction

The models used in this study receive input data on both internal and external temperatures in order to predict the thermal sensation of occupants. The thermal feedback information of personnel is used as the training model’s label. During the experiment stage of this study, the 7-class classification problem was reduced to a 3-class with the categories being: “Neutral”, “Hot”, and “Cold”. Youssef et al. [21] pointed out that the adjacent classes, such as neutral and slightly cool, can not easily distinguish completely from ML algorithms. Because multiple occupants from the same area can answer the questionnaire during the same hour interval, the average

Fig. 1. Overview of the methodology

thermal sensation, ATS_h , based on their votes is calculated as shown in Equation 1:

$$ATS_h = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n TCV_{i,h}, \quad (1)$$

where $TCV_{i,h}$ represents the thermal comfort vote (TCV) value based on the 7-point scale for the i -th measurement taken in hour h , and n is the total number of measurements taken in hour h in the same room of the building. After calculating ATS_h , the numerical values are categorized based on the ASHRAE-55 standard, shown in Equation 2. A zone is considered sufficiently comfortable when the values are between -0.5 and 0.5 on the PMV scale.

$$ATS_h^{cat} = \begin{cases} \text{"Cold"}, & \text{if } ATS_h \leq -0.5 \\ \text{"Neutral"}, & \text{if } -0.5 < ATS_h < 0.5 \\ \text{"Hot"}, & \text{if } ATS_h \geq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

C. Models overview

1) *Thermal Sensation Classification*: Five different state-of-the-art models, including Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) and Ensemble Learning (EL) algorithms, such as XGBoost, RandomForest (RF) and Gradient Boosting (GB), were used for the 3-point scale thermal sensation classification of the occupants that have been extensively used in the relevant literature.

2) *Temperature Forecast*: Long-short Term Memory (LSTM) network was utilized to forecast the hour-ahead internal temperatures of the different rooms in the building and the external temperature. LSTM was chosen due to its demonstrated accuracy in short-term predictions, as evidenced in the relevant literature [22]–[25].

D. Models performance

1) *Classification evaluation*: Evaluation measures play a crucial role in both assessing the classification performance and guiding the classifier modeling [26], [27]. In order to measure the reliability and accuracy of the different ML

models for the multi-classification problem, the weighted averages of precision, recall and F1-score were utilized. In heavy imbalanced datasets, where the number of samples in some classes is much smaller than others, the use of the weighted average is recommended as the macro average may be heavily influenced by the performance of the dominant classes.

Weighted average precision:

$$precision_{weighted} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \quad (3)$$

Weighted average recall:

$$recall_{weighted} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} \quad (4)$$

Weighted average F1-score:

$$F1_{weighted} = 2 \cdot \frac{precision_{weighted} \cdot recall_{weighted}}{precision_{weighted} + recall_{weighted}} \quad (5)$$

where TP_i , FP_i , and FN_i represent the number of true positives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively, for class i , and w_i is the weight assigned to class i .

2) *Forecast evaluation*: The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is a widely used metric for evaluating the accuracy of time series forecasting models, including those based on LSTM networks. MAPE measures the average percentage difference between the actual values and the predicted values, expressed as a percentage of the actual values. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is another commonly used metric for evaluating the accuracy of time series forecasting models [28], [29]. RMSE measures the average magnitude of the error between the actual values and the predicted values. The formulas for MAPE and RMSE are the following:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{actual_i - forecast_i}{actual_i} \right| \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (actual_i - forecast_i)^2} \quad (7)$$

where n is the number of observations in the time series.

III. EXPERIMENTAL APPLICATION

A. Data analysis

The validation and testing of the aforementioned methodology were conducted at the ASM Headquarters, which comprises six office rooms across three floors, each divided into two zones (north and south). Internal temperature was measured in each room using sensors, while also a sensor was installed outdoors to measure the external temperature. Initially, the occupants of all rooms completed the questionnaire in specific time intervals for the month of November and a total of 1429 votes from 180 employees were collected. Based on the answers about their thermal sensation, most occupants of the building were feeling comfortable (66.5%) as shown in

Figure 2. However, according to ASHRAE-55 standard, the comfort zone is considered to be sufficiently comfortable if at least 80% of its occupants can be expected to not object to the ambient condition and so further improvements on the existing HVAC control are required.

A comparative analysis was also conducted between hourly average thermal sensation of the different offices, as calculated based on Eq. 1, and the PMV using measured internal temperatures and assumptions that commonly used for the indoor environmental conditions regarding office buildings, which are shown in the following table.

TABLE II
ASSUMED PARAMETERS USED FOR CALCULATING THE PMV IN THE OFFICE BUILDING.

Parameter	Value
Mean radiant temperature	Equal to the internal temperature
Relative humidity	60%
Air speed	0.1 m/s
Metabolic rate	1.2 met (seated office work)
Clothing insulation	1.0 clo (typical office attire in November)

Looking at the histograms of Figure 3 and based on the PMV, most occupants are dissatisfied with the thermal conditions as most values are concentrated outside the comfortable range ($-0.5 \leq PMV \leq 0.5$). This is not case when taking into consideration the thermal sensation of the occupants based on their votes, where in most of the hours the indoor conditions were sufficiently comfortable. For that reason, the PMV method is not reliable in our case as it relies on many estimated and assumed values, which can wrongly report dissatisfaction of the occupants.

Afterwards, the number of each class in the proposed 3-point scale thermal sensation was calculated to identify the correct metric for evaluating the classification models. Based on Eq. 2, there were 114 records where the ATS_h^{cat} was categorized as "neutral", while 33 and 12 were categorized as "cold" and "hot" respectively. The results indicate that the data is skewed with 72% of them being in one class and so the selection of weighted average evaluation metrics was deemed suitable.

1) *Algorithm results:* The below tables show the performance of the selected ML classification algorithms on two datasets, one using only the internal temperature data of each room and the other using both the internal and external temperature data.

TABLE III
WEIGHTED PRECISION FOR THE SEVERAL MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS (HIGHEST PERFORMANCE FOR EVALUATION METRIC IS BOLDED).

Model	Weighted precision (%)	
	Internal temperature data only	Internal and external temperature data
LR	75.4	75.4
DT	66.5	70.3
SVM	67.1	73.9
kNN	71.0	71.0
XGBoost	70.0	72.0
GB	65.3	69.8
RF	67.1	74.9

TABLE IV
WEIGHTED RECALL FOR THE SEVERAL MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS (HIGHEST PERFORMANCE FOR EVALUATION METRIC IS BOLDED).

Model	Weighted recall (%)	
	Internal temperature data only	Internal and external temperature data
LR	78.1	78.1
DT	71.9	73.4
SVM	78.1	79.7
kNN	78.1	76.6
XGBoost	76.6	68.8
GB	73.4	65.6
RF	75.0	78.1

TABLE V
WEIGHTED F1-SCORE FOR THE SEVERAL MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS (HIGHEST PERFORMANCE FOR EVALUATION METRIC IS BOLDED).

Model	Weighted F1-score (%)	
	Internal temperature data only	Internal and external temperature data
LR	71.9	71.9
DT	67.9	70.3
SVM	71.9	74.3
kNN	73.7	72.2
XGBoost	71.6	69.1
GB	68.3	65.3
RF	69.5	76.8

The results suggest that using both internal and external temperature data can improve the performance of the machine learning algorithms in predicting the average thermal sensation. Looking at the F1-score results, we can see that the kNN algorithm performs the best on the dataset that uses only internal temperature data, achieving a score of 73.7%. However, on the dataset that uses both internal and external temperature data, the RF algorithm achieves the highest F1-score of 76.8%, followed closely by the SVM algorithm with a score of 74.3%.

The following table presents the evaluation results of LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) networks that were used to forecast the hour-ahead temperature values of both internal and external environments in a building.

TABLE VI
EVALUATION OF LSTM NETWORKS DEPLOYED FOR THE HOUR-AHEAD FORECAST OF THE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL TEMPERATURES.

Temperature data	Floor	Zone	MAPE (%)	RMSE (%)
Internal	Ground	North	1.24	0.29
	Ground	South	1.14	0.43
	First	North	1.59	0.43
	First	South	0.91	0.26
	Second	North	1.78	0.57
	Second	South	1.14	0.30
External	-	-	12.01	0.58

The results show that the LSTM networks achieved relatively high accuracy in forecasting the temperature values, with MAPE ranging from 0.91% to 12.01% and RMSE ranging from 0.26% to 0.58%. The internal temperature predictions were more accurate than the external temperature predictions, which is expected since the internal temperature values are affected by more stable factors such as building construction, insulation, and the HVAC system, whereas the external

Fig. 2. Percentage of the total number of thermal comfort votes about their thermal sensation on the 7-point scale collected for the month of November.

Fig. 3. Histograms of Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and Thermal Sensation based on TCV_h for the month of November.

temperature values are influenced by multiple factors such as weather conditions and location. One of the reasons why LSTM networks performed so well is because they can capture long-term dependencies in the input sequence, which is critical in time-series forecasting. Additionally, the networks were fed with a large amount of historical data (approximately two years' worth of data), which enabled them to learn the underlying patterns in the data and make accurate predictions. Due to the high accuracy of the LSTM networks, the forecasted internal and external temperatures can be used as inputs to the classification models to predict the hour-ahead average thermal sensation.

Finally, an evaluation of the prediction of the thermal sensation in the building was conducted based on the responses from the occupants that used the deployed web application. A total of 542 votes were collected and the ATS_h of the different rooms at different hour intervals was calculated and categorized on the 3-point scale based on the described methodology. In order, to evaluate how the different model performed on predicting the ATS_h^{cat} , the weighted F1-score was used.

RF still performed the best when using both the internal and external data and scored 72.4% on the evaluation metric, a reduction of 4.4% compared to the training set. Meanwhile, XGBoost was the best-performing model using only

TABLE VII
WEIGHTED F1-SCORE ON THE VALIDATION DATA FOR THE SEVERAL MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS (HIGHEST PERFORMANCE FOR EVALUATION METRIC IS BOLDED).

Model	Weighted F1-score (%)	
	Internal temperature data only	Internal and external temperature data
LR	70.9	70.9
DT	65.8	68.8
SVM	70.9	72.2
kNN	71.1	70.8
XGBoost	71.2	67.2
GB	67.2	62.3
RF	68.4	72.4

the internal temperature data with an f1-score of 71.2%. A smaller reduction in the error is seen in the models using only the internal temperature data, which is probably due to the uncertainty that the predicted external temperature feeds the models. The next step is to once again train the models with the new data from the web application and evaluate them. Overall, all the ML models showed an improvement on the different evaluation metrics, as more data were fed into them with RF being the best-performing model with a weighted average f1-score of 80.1%.

The results of the evaluation demonstrate the effectiveness of the chosen classification models in accurately predicting the thermal sensation of the occupants and provide valuable insights for building managers to adjust temperature settings to maintain occupant comfort.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper presents a machine learning-based approach for assessing and improving thermal comfort control in buildings. The approach utilizes temperature sensors and feedback from occupants to estimate thermal sensation and support HVAC control actions. The effectiveness of the proposed approach was demonstrated through testing at the ASM Headquarters. Results from the evaluation of the prediction of average thermal sensation in different rooms using the different classification models showed constant improvements, with the

RF model achieving more than 80% weighted average f1-score. The approach presented in this paper offers an accurate and efficient way to manage thermal comfort in buildings, providing valuable insights for building managers to adjust temperature settings and maintain occupant comfort while also promoting energy efficiency. In future work, it would be interesting to explore the use of weather forecasts as inputs to the ML models, instead of relying solely on the prediction of external temperature. Weather forecasts could provide more accurate and reliable information about outdoor conditions and help improve the accuracy of thermal comfort predictions. Another avenue for future research is to collect more responses from occupants using the online web application. This would provide a larger and more diverse dataset, which could help to further improve the accuracy of the ML models. Finally, the proposed approach can be integrated with advanced HVAC control systems that can automatically adjust the temperature and ventilation settings in real-time based on the predicted thermal comfort of the occupants, thereby improving the energy efficiency of the building while maintaining occupant comfort.

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